

Changing dynamics of management education by Prof. (Dr.) Atul Kumar

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Change is the only constant thing and management education is no exception. While management education is constantly evolving, below are the key impact factors that will drive future changes.

First, technology will be one of the most important skills to be learned. Data is the next oil and big data, AI, data analytics, etc. skills will be in high demand. Not only the new economy sectors but the traditional ones will demand data analysis skills. The growing digitalization of businesses will mean, students, are well equipped with advanced technology skills.

Second, the emphasis on soft skills and communication will remain a key attribute. Management graduates are not only expected to possess diverse and all-round business skills but also soft skills especially communication. While the stringent admission process takes care of technical aspects, the management course is expected to hone soft skills such as communication, leadership, teamwork, problem-solving, ethics, and interpersonal skills. There is broad consensus that the ultimate success in the career depends on the emotional competence aspects.

Third, is the international exposure. Day by day businesses are getting global and international experience is becoming more relevant. Many management courses require students to study one of the foreign languages. One of the other trends is that many institutes have a tie-up with international b-schools and the students get to spend a semester with the international partner institutions. International internships are another way by which students get the much-required international exposure and have the potential to grab plum international jobs.

Fourth, is entrepreneurship. This era is characterized by start-ups. Many students prefer not to follow the conventional job route for their careers but instead choose to start their own ventures. Clearly what is expected of the management course is to equip the students with the required entrepreneurship skills. Many leading institutes have business incubation centers and if the students have some original ideas and the drive to launch their own venture the institutes offer all the help and the required environment.

Fifth, is the changes forced upon by the covid-19 pandemic. The covid-19 crisis has changed most of the things around us. The challenges also opened up new opportunities such as online learning. Nobody would have imagined such a dramatic shift and the success of online learning. The post-covid world will continue to see online teaching albeit at a lower scale.

In summary, the future of management courses will demand more of technology skills, will continue to focus on soft skills, will be more global than current and more dynamic in terms of entrepreneurship and last but not the least, more agile to cope up with crisis such as the covid-19.

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